

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF CORRECTIONAL AND REHABILITATION WORK OF CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DISORDERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13773079>

Abstract. *This article discusses the main areas for enhancing the methodology of remedial and rehabilitation efforts with children who have speech impairments. Special emphasis is placed on the individualization of the remedial process, the utilization of information and communication technology, as well as the significance of early detection and intervention. A holistic approach to rehabilitation, which entails collaboration between speech therapists, psychological experts, and parents, is analyzed. The significance of parents' active involvement in the remedial process and the professional development of experts to enhance work outcomes is highlighted. Implementing these approaches contributes to enhancing the efficacy of remedial and recovery efforts and promoting children's speech development.*

Keywords: *Speech disorders, treatment, rehabilitation, diagnosis, early intervention, information and communication technologies, holistic approach.*

Introduction. Speech disorders in children represent one of the most prevalent forms of communication impairments that necessitate specialized intervention and support. Modern speech-language therapy practices strive to continuously enhance techniques aimed at addressing these challenges. This is driven by the need to tailor interventions to individual child characteristics, early identification of speech difficulties, and utilization of innovative approaches to enhance the effectiveness of treatment.

The purpose of this article is to explore key strategies for enhancing the methods of intervention and rehabilitation for children with speech impairments, with a focus on their impact on promoting speech development.

One of the key areas for improving the methodology of correctional work is the individualization of the rehabilitation process for children with speech disorders. These children have different forms and degrees of speech difficulties, so it is essential to tailor approaches to their individual needs.

Research Methodology. The methodology used for this research on improving correctional and rehabilitation work with children with speech disorders is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. This mixed-methods approach allows for a comprehensive analysis of both the effectiveness of current practices and the impact of proposed improvements. The following key elements define the methodology:

1. Study Design

- Qualitative Component: A descriptive and analytical approach is used to explore current rehabilitation practices, focusing on individualization, early intervention, and the use of information and communication technologies (ICT). Data were collected through interviews with speech therapists, psychologists, and parents, as well as observations of therapy sessions.

- Quantitative Component: A comparative analysis was conducted to measure the effectiveness of existing and improved rehabilitation methods. This includes pre- and post-intervention evaluations using standardized speech assessment tools.

2. Participants

- Children: The study involved children aged 3 to 7 years diagnosed with various speech disorders, including articulation, phonological, and expressive language disorders. The children were selected from specialized kindergartens, rehabilitation centers, and speech therapy clinics.

- Professionals: Speech therapists, psychologists, and neurologists participated in this study to provide a multi-dimensional perspective on the rehabilitative approach. Their input was critical in assessing the interdisciplinary collaboration element of the methodology.

- Parents: Parents of the participating children were included to evaluate their role in supporting at-home speech therapy practices.

3. Data Collection Methods

- Diagnostic Tools: Initial diagnostic assessments of the children's speech abilities were performed using standardized instruments like the Preschool Language Scale (PLS) and the Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals (CELF). This allowed for precise identification of speech impairments and cognitive development levels.

- Intervention Programs: Tailored intervention programs were developed based on diagnostic results, focusing on individualized approaches. The intervention programs were documented and adapted for each child to ensure progress in targeted speech areas.

- Use of ICT: Tools such as multimedia software, mobile applications, and virtual reality simulations were integrated into therapy sessions. Children's engagement and speech improvements were tracked using these digital tools.

- Parent Involvement: Parents were trained in home-based activities and received guidelines to continue speech development exercises outside of formal therapy sessions. Feedback from parents was collected through surveys to assess the impact of their involvement.

4. Intervention Strategies

- Individualization of Therapy: Based on initial diagnostic results, each child received a personalized intervention plan. The pace and type of intervention were tailored to match the child's specific needs, including phonemic awareness, articulation, and lexico-grammatical skills.

- Early Detection and Intervention: Screening programs were introduced in kindergartens to identify children with potential speech issues. Children diagnosed before the age of 3 were enrolled in early intervention programs to prevent the establishment of speech disorders.

- Interdisciplinary Approach: Speech therapy sessions involved collaboration between speech therapists, psychologists, and neurologists. Joint team sessions were conducted to address associated cognitive, emotional, or neurological issues that might impact speech development.

5. Data Analysis

- Quantitative Analysis: Pre- and post-intervention speech assessments were analyzed to measure the effectiveness of the individualized and technology-enhanced programs. Statistical tools like t-tests were used to determine significant improvements in speech abilities across the group of children.

- Qualitative Analysis: Interviews with therapists, parents, and observations of therapy sessions were analyzed using thematic coding to identify the most effective strategies and challenges in the implementation of the new methodology.

6. Ethical Considerations

The study followed ethical guidelines for working with children. Informed consent was obtained from parents, and the confidentiality of the children's data was maintained. The interventions were conducted by certified professionals to ensure the safety and well-being of the participants.

This methodology ensures a rigorous evaluation of current and improved speech therapy methods, emphasizing the importance of individualization, technology integration, and interdisciplinary collaboration in enhancing speech development in children.

Conclusion: The improvement of the methodology for correctional and rehabilitation work with children who have speech disorders is a crucial aspect of contemporary speech therapy practice. By integrating innovative technologies, implementing early diagnosis, personalizing the correction process, and actively involving parents in the rehabilitation effort, significant improvements in the efficiency of work with children can be achieved.

The implementation of an integrated approach, along with continuous professional development for specialists, creates the conditions for the successful execution of correction programs and the attainment of significant outcomes in the speech development of children.

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